

Carbon-13 NMR Chemical Shifts of Some Dicoumarols and Benzopyranodicoumarins

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Carbon-13 nmr chemical shifts of a number of dicoumarols and benzopyranodicoumarins are studied.

In our continued work in the field of coumarins¹, we report here the carbon-13 nmr chemical shifts of some of the dicoumarins. They are divided into two groups – dicoumarols (1-11) and benzopyranodicoumarins (12-15).

Results and Discussion

The carbon-13 nmr chemical shifts of the dicoumarols, viz. 1-phenyldicoumarol (1), 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (2), 1-(2-methoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (3), 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)dicoumarol (4), 1-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (5), 1-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (6), 1-(2,3,4-trimethoxyphenyl)dicoumarol (7), 1-(3,4,5-trimethoxy-

phenyl)dicoumarol (8), 1-(2-benzyloxyphenyl)dicoumarol (9), 1-(3-methoxy-4-benzyloxyphenyl)dicoumarol (10), 1-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)dicoumarol (11), and the benzopyranodicoumarins, viz. 6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (12), 6-(4-acetoxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (13), 3,4-di-methoxy-6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (14), 3,4-methylenedioxy-6-(4-hydroxycoumarin-3-yl)-6*H*,7*H*-benzopyrano[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran-7-one (15) are enumerated in the Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1- ¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ, ppm) OF COMPOUNDS 1-11

Carbon no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
C-2	169.0	165.2	166.8	168.4	164.8	164.8	164.5	164.9	167.6	166.8	165.2
C-3	105.0	104.7	104.0	104.7	105.3	104.6	105.6	104.3	105.5	104.6	104.8
C-4	165.0	165.0	164.4	165.8	164.2	164.8	163.3	164.8	163.7	163.5	165.0
C-4a	116.4	117.8	119.8	118.6	117.8	117.6	117.1	116.5	116.6	116.4	117.6
C-5	124.6	124.1	124.0	125.2	124.0	123.9	124.1	124.8	124.2	124.8	124.1
C-6	124.1	123.4	124.0	124.2	123.6	123.9	123.7	124.1	124.0	123.9	124.1
C-7	132.6	132.0	130.7	132.0	132.2	132.0	132.1	132.7	132.0	133.6	132.3
C-8	116.4	116.5	115.5	116.7	116.4	116.0	116.2	116.5	116.1	117.0	116.3
C-8a	152.2	152.3	152.4	153.6	152.3	152.2	152.1	153.2	151.8	152.9	152.4
-CH	36.0	35.4	33.0	37.2	32.8	35.7	32.7	36.1	33.3	35.6	36.0
C-1'	135.0	124.1	119.6	143.9	107.1	123.9	107.0	124.8	120.3	124.7	133.3
C-2'	126.3	128.0	157.4	113.1	159.7	111.6	151.7	104.3	156.6	113.3	107.7
C-3'	128.4	114.6	111.1	158.1	99.2	148.7	142.1	153.2	111.3	150.0	147.7
C-4'	126.6	157.6	128.9	114.9	158.7	147.3	152.5	130.7	128.2	146.6	145.6
C-5'	128.4	113.8	123.0	129.8	104.5	111.7	105.6	152.3	123.4	113.3	108.0
C-6'	126.3	128.0	126.6	120.8	133.1	119.0	122.4	104.3	128.2	119.4	119.8
-CH ₂ -									70.0	70.9	101.0
2'-OMe			55.6		56.0		60.2				
3'-OMe						55.6	60.2	56.2			
4'-OMe		55.2			55.5	55.7	55.8	60.7		56.3	
5'-OMe								56.2			
C-1''									135.4	136.8	
C-2'', C-6''									127.5	127.6	
C-3'', C-5''									127.8	128.3	
C-4''									127.2	127.1	

TABLE 2— ^{13}C NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ , ppm) OF COMPOUNDS 12-15

Carbon no.	12	13	14	15
C-1a	149.3	149.3	149.2	149.0
C-2	122.3	122.6	101.3	98.3
C-3	128.7	129.1	146.8	145.2
C-4	122.7	123.2	143.5	145.2
C-5	128.4	128.8	111.0	107.0
C-5a	116.2	115.8	113.0	
C-6	28.8	30.3	29.1	30.2
C-6a	100.8	99.8	100.5	
C-7	160.5		161.2	
C-8a	152.1	152.4	152.3	
C-9	116.2	116.4	116.7	116.2
C-10	132.2	131.9	132.7	131.9
C-11	123.9	123.2	123.1	123.3
C-12	124.0	124.0	124.5	124.3
C-12a	113.9		114.3	
C-12b	152.1	152.4	152.6	153.0
C-2'	160.8		161.2	161.7
C-3'	100.8	99.8	100.5	
C-4'	156.4		157.0	
C-4'a		120.2		
C-5'	125.4	125.5	125.0	124.9
C-6'	124.5	124.0	124.5	123.8
C-7'	132.5	132.1	132.9	132.7
C-8'	116.5	116.6	116.8	116.9
C-8'a	152.3	152.6	152.3	153.0
3-OMe			56.3	
4-OMe			56.3	
OCOMe		167.2		
OCOMe		20.3		
OCH ₂ O				101.7

- 1 $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}$
- 2 $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = \text{H}, R^3 = \text{OCH}_3$
- 3 $R^1 = \text{OCH}_3, R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}$
- 4 $R^1 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}, R^2 = \text{OH}$
- 5 $R^1 = R^3 = \text{OCH}_3, R^2 = R^4 = \text{H}$
- 6 $R^1 = R^4 = \text{H}, R^2 = R^3 = \text{OCH}_3$
- 7 $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = \text{OCH}_3, R^4 = \text{H}$
- 8 $R^1 = \text{H}, R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{OCH}_3$
- 9 $R^1 = \text{OBn}, R^2 = R^3 = R^4 = \text{H}$
- 10 $R^1 = R^4 = \text{H}, R^2 = \text{OCH}_3, R^3 = \text{OBn}$
- 11 $R^1 = R^4 = \text{H}, R^2 - R^3 = \text{OCH}_2\text{O}$

The carbon-13 spectral analysis of these compounds were made following mutual correlation and consideration of the carbon-13 spectrum of 1-phenyldicoumarol². 1-Phenyldicoumarol shows seven signals resonating at δ

132.6, 128.4, 126.6, 126.3, 124.6, 124.1 and 116.4 ppm for thirteen methine carbons. Out of these signals, the peaks at δ 132.6, 124.6, 124.1 and 116.4 ppm are related to C-7, C-5, C-6 and C-8 carbons respectively of the two coumarin moieties. The signals at δ 128.4, 126.6 and 126.3 ppm are assigned to C-3' (and C-5'), C-4' and C-2' (and C-6') carbons respectively, of the phenyl ring. The chemical shifts at δ 169.0, 165.0, 152.2, 135.0, 116.4 and 105.0 ppm are due to the C-2, C-4, C-8a, C-1', C-4a and C-3 quaternary carbons respectively.

In the carbon-13 nmr spectra of compounds 1-11, the carbonyl carbons appear near δ 165-169 ppm. The C-4 carbons resonate around δ 165 ppm. The resonating frequencies at *ca.* δ 152 and 132 ppm are assignable to C-8a and C-7 carbons respectively. The signals near δ 124 ppm are due to C-5 and C-6 carbons. The chemical shifts near δ 116-119 ppm are assigned to C-4a carbons. The C-8 and C-3 carbons resonate near δ 116 and δ 105 ppm respectively.

The effect of introducing oxygenated substituents on the phenyl ring needs to be explicated. It is followed from the additivity rules³ that the introduction of a methoxy function in the aromatic ring causes deshielding of the C-1 carbon atom (+30.2 ppm), along with the shielding of *ortho* and *para* carbon atoms (-15.5 and -8.9 ppm respectively)

- 12 $R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = \text{H}$
- 13 $R^1 = \text{Ac}, R^2 = R^3 = \text{H}$
- 14 $R^1 = \text{H}, R^2 = R^3 = \text{OCH}_3$
- 15 $R^1 = \text{H}, R^2 - R^3 = \text{OCH}_2\text{O}$

and the *meta* carbons remain practically unaffected. It is observed from the Table 1 that simple additivity rules hold good for compounds 2-4 and 9 where the phenyl ring contains only one oxygen substitution. In the case of compounds 6, 10 and 11 having two oxygenated functions at C-3' and C-4' positions, the carbon-13 chemical shifts follow the additivity rules except some of the signals, which are discussed herewith. The appearance of C-1' carbon at δ 133 ppm in 11 notwithstanding the chemical shift for the same carbon near δ 124 ppm in 6 and 10 indicates that some deshielding mechanism is operative on this carbon. The operation of some shielding effects (*ca.* 6 ppm) on C-2' and C-5' carbons in 11 is also noted when compared with similar carbons in 6 and 10. It is also noteworthy to record that the deshielding mechanism is also operative on C-6' carbon of 5.

The deviation of the additivity rules are quite remarkable when the phenyl ring contains three oxygen sub-

stituents on contiguous carbon but free from steric interaction with the fourth substituent as in **8**, the chemical shift of each of the carbons of the phenyl nucleus (when compared with those of **6**) are largely affected by the presence of a methoxy group at C-5' position. The introduction of a methoxy group at C-5' position of compound **6** leading to the compound **8** causes the central methoxy group (at C-4') to go out of the plane of the phenyl ring resulting in decreasing its shielding effects on *ortho* and *para* carbons (C-3', C-5' and C-1' carbons) and consequently comparatively higher chemical shift values on these carbons are observed. Similarly, in compound **7** where all the four substituents are on the contiguous carbons, the methoxy groups at C-2' and C-3' are forced to go out of the plane of the phenyl ring. In view of this effect, the methoxy groups at C-2' and C-3' exert less *ortho* and *para* substituent effects. The out of planarity of the C-4' methoxy group in **8** and methoxy groups at C-2' and C-3' in **7** are also evidenced from the appearance of these methoxy signals at about 5 ppm more downfield than the normal methoxy signals.

For compounds **12-15**, the carbon-13 nmr chemical shifts (Table 2) of C-6a, C-7 and C-12b carbons resonate at upfield region with respect to the corresponding carbons (C-3, C-2 and C-4) of compounds **1-11**. A significant shielding of *ca.* 12 ppm is observed on C-12b in **12-15**. This clearly indicates that some shielding effects are operating on them. This shielding effect is presumably due to the fact that the 4-hydroxyl group of one coumarin moiety forms cyclic ring with the phenyl nucleus. The operation of some shielding mechanism on C-2', C-3' and C-4' carbons in **12-15** is also noticed.

Experimental

The carbon-13 nmr spectra were recorded on Bruker AM-300L and Varian CFT-20 nmr spectrometers operating at 75.47 and 20.1 MHz respectively in FT mode. These spectrometers were equipped with ASPECT 300 and VDM 620L computers respectively. The compounds were submitted to decoupling, single frequency off-resonance decoupling (SFORD) and attached proton test (APT) to establish the carbon shifts and the degree of protonations. The samples were run in CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆ as solvents as well as internal lock and internal reference. All solutions were *ca.* 5-15% (w/v) in concentration. The chemical shifts reported are in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS; $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$ ppm and $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{DMSO-d}_6} + 39.6$ ppm. The spectra were run with sweep width 4000 and 15000 Hz, pulse width 6 and 3 μ s and approximately 2s pulse repetition time. Synthesis of the compounds **1-15** will be reported elsewhere.

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